

“GREEN” COMPOSITES USING MODIFIED SOY PROTEIN CONCENTRATE AND WOVEN FLAX FABRIC

by

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ABSTRACT

“Green” composites made from environment-friendly, fully biodegradable resins and fibers offer an attractive alternative to the conventional composites made using petroleum-based or synthetic resins and fibers that do not degrade over many years. Woven fabric reinforced composite offer several advantages over unidirectional composites such as good stability in mutually orthogonal warp and weft direction, more balance properties in the fabric plane and better impact resistance.

This paper discusses two-dimensional ‘green’ composites prepared using glutaraldehyde modified soy protein concentrate (MSPC) and flax fabric. Soy protein concentrate (SPC) polymer has low tensile properties, poor moisture resistance and is brittle. SPC polymer with 15% glycerin, as an external plasticizer, exhibited fracture stress and Young’s modulus of 17 MPa and 368 MPa, respectively. In the present study, SPC was cross-linked with glutaraldehyde (GA) to increase its tensile properties and improve its processability as a resin to manufacture flax fabric reinforced composites.

SPC forms a miscible blend with GA and reacts with free amine groups in the protein. MSPC showed 35% increase in fracture stress and 55% increase in Young’s modulus as well as improved moisture resistance compared to SPC. Besides mechanical properties, MSPC was also characterized for its thermo-gravimetric and dynamic mechanical properties.

Composite laminates, approximately 1 mm thick, were made using flax fabric and MSPC polymer. Composite specimens were prepared with two different orientations, namely, 0° and 90°. Composite specimens exhibited a fracture stress of 56 MPa and 42 MPa in the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively. The laminates exhibited a Young’s modulus of 1.3 GPa and 1.09 GPa in the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively.

Key Terms: Green composites, soy protein concentrate, fabric reinforced composites, flax woven fabric, glutaraldehyde

1. INTRODUCTION

Conventionally, most of the composites are made by combining synthetic fibers and polymers. Most of these fibers and resins are made from non-biodegradable, petroleum-based chemicals that do not degrade over several decades. According to United States Environment Protection Agency (EPA), 4025 metric tons of plastic waste is produced each year aboard government ships alone (Sue et al., 1997). With an increase in environmental awareness and stringent environmental laws, manufacturers are looking towards ‘greener’ and more environment friendly alternatives for conventional plastics and polymers (Netravali and Chabba, 2003). Considerable research in this field has been focused on developing natural fiber reinforced composites using non biodegradable

resins such as polyethylene, polypropylene and epoxy (Belcher et al., 2001; Bhattacharayya et al., 2003; Kajaks et al., 2001). Although these composites may have good properties, they are only partially biodegradable and can neither return to an industrial metabolism nor to a natural metabolism after their useful life. As a result, they are difficult to even downcycle and be reused (Netravali and Chabba, 2003).

In the present research, plain woven flax fabric and modified soy protein concentrate (MSPC) were used to make completely biodegradable and environment friendly ‘green’ composites. Flax is a bast fiber obtained from an annual plant, *Linum usitatissimum*, which is grown in temperate and sub tropical regions (Cook, 1964). Table 1 (Saheb and Jog, 1999) compares the properties of flax with E glass fiber. It is evident that flax is lighter and has a higher specific modulus than glass fiber, making it a good alternative for glass fiber reinforced plastics. Flax, like other natural fibers, also offers the benefit of good insulating and sound damping properties due to its cellular and hollow structure.

Soy protein is commercially available as soy protein isolate (SPI) and soy protein concentrate (SPC). Chemically, SPI has 90% protein while SPC has 70% protein, 18% carbohydrates, 6% ash and remaining is fiber and moisture. Soybean protein contains several amino acids such as glutamic acid, argenine, lysine, cystine and aspartic acid that have polar groups. These groups can act as useful cross-linking and/or hydrogen bonding sites to improve the mechanical properties of soy protein polymer. Lodha and Netravali (Lodha and Netravali, 2002) used SPI as a resin in ramie fiber reinforced random, short fiber composites while Nam and Netravali (Nam and Netravali, 2002) used SPC and ramie fibers to make unidirectional reinforced composites with tensile strengths upto 275 MPa.

Table 1 Properties of Flax and Glass Fibers

Fiber	Specific Gravity	Tensile Strength, MPa	Modulus, GPa	Specific Modulus
Flax	1.5	344	27	50
E Glass	2.5	3400	72	28

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 MATERIALS

ARCON[®] S, soy protein concentrate powder was provided by Archer Daniels Midland Company, IL. Analytical grade glycerin and sodium hydroxide were obtained from Fisher Scientific, PA. Glutaric dialdehyde (glutaraldehyde), 25 wt.% solution in water, was obtained from Aldrich Chemical Company, WI. All chemicals were used as received, without any further treatment. Woven flax fabric was provided by Sachdeva Fabrics Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, India. Bleached flax fabric was obtained and was used without any further treatment.

2.2 FABRIC CHARACTERIZATION

Woven flax fabric was characterized for its thickness, warp and weft crimp, fabric count, weave and tensile properties in both longitudinal and transverse directions. For all of these tests, fabric specimens were conditioned at standard ASTM atmosphere (65% r.h. and 21°C) for 5 days. Fabric thickness was measured on Sherman W. Frazier Compressometer according to ASTM D 1777-96. A circular presser foot, 9.525 mm in diameter was used for measuring the fabric thickness. Twenty measurements were made to obtain an average value for the fabric thickness. Warp and weft crimp were determined in accordance with modified ASTM D 3883-99. Since no tension device was available, yarn crimp was removed by hand using extreme care. Warp and weft linear densities (denier) were measured according to ASTM D 1059-97. Ten linear density measurements were performed for warp and weft yarns each, to obtain the average warp and weft denier. Fabric specimens were observed under a 25 mm pick counting glass, to determine the warp and weft interlacement pattern and to obtain its weave structure.

Flax fabrics were tensile tested according to ASTM D 5035-95 using Instron tensile tester, model 1122. Tensile properties such as fracture stress, fracture strain and Young's modulus were characterized. Tests were performed at a gauge length of 50 mm and a strain rate of 1 min⁻¹. Twenty specimens were characterized in both warp and weft directions.

2.3 SPC AND MSPC CURING

SPC powder was processed to make it suitable as a resin for 'green' composite fabrication. Similar processing technique has been used earlier for SPC (Nam, 2002). SPC powder was mixed with distilled and deionized water in a beaker, in a ratio of 1:13 (w/w) and 15% glycerin was added as a plasticizer. The solution was homogenized using a magnetic stirrer for 15 minutes and then the pH of the solution was adjusted to 11±0.1, using 1N NaOH solution. SPC solution was again stirred for 15 minutes and then the beaker was transferred to a water bath maintained at 70°C. The solution was stirred in a water bath for 30 minutes at a constant temperature of 70°C. This 'pre-cured' solution was cast on Teflon[®] coated glass plates and dried in Fischer Isotemp oven at 35°C for 20 hours. Finally, the dried soy protein polymer sheets were hot pressed (cured) in Carver Hydraulic hot press, model 3891-4PROA00, at 120°C for 25 minutes under a pressure of 7 MPa.

To cross-link SPC with glutaraldehyde (GA), desired amounts (10 to 50%, w/w) of GA were added to SPC solution while in a water bath, after 27 minutes of pre-curing at 70°C. The pre-cured SPC polymer was dried at room temperature and cured using the same curing cycle, as described above for SPC. Henceforth in this paper GA modified SPC will be referred as MSPC.

2.4 CHARACTERIZATION OF SPC AND MSPC POLYMERS

SPC and MSPC polymers were characterized for their tensile, dynamic mechanical and thermal properties. The cured SPC and MSPC polymer sheets were conditioned at standard ASTM atmosphere (65% r.h. and 21°C) for 3 days prior to performing these tests.

Tensile properties such as fracture stress, fracture strain and Young's modulus of SPC and MSPC polymers were characterized in accordance with ASTM D 882-97. The tests were performed using an Instron tensile tester, model 1122, at a strain rate of 1 min⁻¹ and a gauge length of 50 mm. Dynamic mechanical properties of SPC and MSPC polymers were measured using TA

Instruments Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA), model DMA 2980, at Cornell Center for Materials Research (CCMR) facilities. The specimens were scanned from 0°C to 250°C at a ramp rate of 5°C/min. Thermo-gravimetric properties of polymers were measured using TA Instruments Thermo-gravimetric Analyzer (TGA), model 2050. The specimens were scanned from 25°C to 350°C at a ramp rate of 10°C/min.

2.5 COMPOSITES FABRICATION

Two dimensional (2D) flax fabric reinforced composites were fabricated using MSPC resin. Flax fabric strips, 2.5 cm wide and 13 cm long, were cut in desired direction (weft wise/longitudinal or warp wise/transverse). Weight of the fabric strips was recorded to evaluate the weight fraction of the fabric in the composite and four fabric strips were used for each composite specimen fabrication. Composites were prepared with all four layers oriented at either 0° or 90°. MSPC resin was prepared as described in section 2.3. Fabric strips were held under tension, using masking tape, in a glass container. Precured resin was poured over the fabric strips and allowed to penetrate for 15 min at room temperature. The resin coated fabric strips were then transferred to a Teflon[®] coated glass plate and more resin was applied in between the layers using a paintbrush. The composite specimens were then, allowed to dry in an oven at 35°C for approximately 26 hr. Care was taken to make sure that the specimens were neither totally dry nor completely wet before hot pressing. These specimens were then transferred into a mold for hot pressing. Mold-releasing agent was used to facilitate the removal of composites after curing. Curing was performed in Carver Hydraulic hot press, model 3891-4PROA00, at 120°C for 25 min at a pressure of 8 MPa.

2.6 COMPOSITES CHARACTERIZATION

Tensile properties of fabric reinforced composites were characterized in accordance with ASTM D 3039/D3039M-00. Three thickness measurements were performed along the length of each specimen and the average value was used for calculating the fracture stress, fracture strain and Young's modulus. The tests were performed on the Instron tensile tester, model 1122, at a strain rate of 1 min⁻¹ and a gauge length of 50 mm. A minimum of five specimens were tested to obtain the average tensile properties.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 FABRIC CHARACTERIZATION

Flax fabric used in this study had a plain weave with an average thickness of 0.39 mm. The warp and weft counts were 402 denier and 453 denier, respectively. The crimp in the warp and the weft yarns were 10.65% and 1.5%, respectively. Tensile properties of the fabric in both longitudinal and transverse directions are summarized in Table 2. As observed in the table, the fracture stress and Young's modulus values of the composite in the longitudinal and the transverse directions are different. This difference can be attributed to the difference in the warp and the weft crimp, which also leads to different fracture strains in the two directions.

3.2 CHARACTERIZATION OF SPC AND MSPC POLYMERS

The average fracture stress and Young's modulus values for SPC polymer with 15% glycerin were found to be 16.9 MPa and 367.6 MPa, respectively. Table 3 summarizes the effect of GA

content on the tensile properties of the MSPC polymer. As can be seen clearly, that increase in GA content leads to an increase in fracture stress and Young's modulus and it also decreases the moisture content of MSPC polymer. This improvement in tensile properties is due to the cross-linking of GA with of amino groups present in SPC. Richards and Knowles (Richard and Knowles, 1968) have proposed that GA reacts with the amino groups in protein to form cross-links. Habeeb and Hiramoto (Habeeb and Hiramoto, 1968) have also proposed that GA reacts with N-terminal amino groups of peptides and the α -amino groups of amino acids.

Table 2 Tensile Properties of Fabric

Fabric Direction	Fracture Stress, MPa	Fracture Strain, %	Young's Modulus, GPa
Transverse [Warp]	33.3 (6.3)*	17.7 (6.2)	0.51 (7.0)
Longitudinal [Weft]	41.2 (10.1)	7.1 (7.8)	1.02 (10.7)

* Figures in parenthesis are CV%

Table 3 Effect of Glutaraldehyde Content on Tensile Properties of MSPC Polymer

GA, % (w/w of SPC)	Fracture Stress, MPa	Fracture Strain, %	Young's Modulus, MPa	Moisture Content, %
00	16.9 (3.8)*	21.9 (10.2)	367.6 (3.3)	15.00
10	18.4 (5.4)	25.4 (12.6)	402.1 (7.9)	14.65
20	18.2 (6.9)	25.0 (14.7)	396.7 (6.2)	14.90
30	19.6 (4.2)	21.5 (13.0)	447.5 (5.9)	14.85
40	19.9 (6.4)	20.9 (14.9)	484.2 (6.7)	13.85
50	22.8 (4.8)	17.2 (13.9)	572.9 (6.3)	13.70

* Figure in parenthesis are CV%

Figure 1 shows the effect of glycerin content on the tensile properties of the MSPC polymer containing 40% GA. Glycerin acts as a plasticizer and hence reducing the glycerin content increases both the fracture stress and Young's modulus values and decreases the fracture strain value significantly. These results are in agreement with the results reported by Lodha and Netravali (Lodha and Netravali, 2002) and Nam (Nam, 2002). For composite preparation, MSPC with 40% GA and 10% glycerin was chosen as the optimum blend percentage.

Figure 1 Effect of Glycerin Content on the Tensile Properties of MSPC Polymer

Figure 2 shows the $\tan \delta$ vs. temperature plots obtained using DMA for SPC and MSPC polymer specimens. It can be seen clearly that crosslinking GA with SPC leads to an increase in glass transition temperature (T_g) from 172°C to 185°C. The β transition temperature also increases from 80°C to 89°C.

Figure 2 Tan δ of SPC and MSPC Polymers

The TGA thermograms of SPC and MSPC polymers are shown in Figure 3. It is evident from the plot that MSPC polymer is stable upto a temperature of 130°C, while SPC starts degrading even below 100°C. Thus, crosslinking SPC with GA leads to better thermal stability of the polymer.

Figure 3 TGA Thermograms of SPC and MSPC Polymers

3.3 CHARACTERIZATION OF COMPOSITE PROPERTIES

Table 4 summarizes the tensile properties of woven fabric reinforced composites, in both longitudinal and transverse directions. The fiber weight fraction in each case was 45%. It is evident from Table 4 that composites have higher fracture stress and Young's modulus but lower fracture strain in the longitudinal direction. This can be attributed primarily to the difference in tensile properties of the fabric in longitudinal and transverse directions.

Table 4 Tensile Properties of Fabric Reinforced Composites

Test Direction	Fracture Stress, MPa	Fracture Strain, %	Young's Modulus, GPa
Longitudinal	55.7 (17.4)*	7.8 (30.9)	1.26 (24.2)
Transverse	42.0 (30.7)	15.5 (67.6)	1.09 (10.7)

*Figures in parenthesis are CV%

4. CONCLUSIONS

SPC was successfully cross-linked with GA and the modified polymer showed 35% increase in fracture stress and 55% increase in Young's modulus. MSPC polymer also exhibited improved moisture resistance and higher thermal stability as compared to SPC. MSPC and flax fabric were used to prepare totally biodegradable 'green' composites. These composites showed moderate strength and can be used in various non-critical applications such as packaging materials.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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